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Rhetorical Devices and Non-verbal Cues: Tools for Effective Political Oratory in India

Harsh Agrawal*

The aim of this paper is to find out rhetorical devices and nonverbal cues present in Indian political speeches. Though many Indian politicians seem to master the art of oratory; their speeches were rarely analyzed. This paper deals with two out of five canons of rhetoric i.e. 'Style' and 'Delivery' in Indian context. Two full-length speeches of 21st century Indian Prime Ministers have been analyzed to find out the purpose served by rhetorical devices and nonverbal cues in Indian context. Although the authenticity of the information produced by the orator has not been checked; the study did reveal different rhetorical devices used by Indian Prime Ministers and their non-verbal cues i.e. facial expressions, intonation, eye-contact, gesture, posture surfaced during speech.

Keywords: Political Oratory, Nonverbal Communication, Rhetoric, Rhetorical Device, Public Speaking

1. Introduction

Oratory has always been an important form of political communication. In today's era, political orators must be skilled communicators. They must have good knowledge of what to say, where to say, whom to say and most importantly how to say. Because the effect produced by their speech is not only limited to the place where it is delivered; rather it crosses boundaries through Social media. For politicians, speechmaking is not just a way of communication with people. Planning as well as executing, both are crucial for producing desired effect. Political leaders address public to put forth their plans, create expectations and for persuasion. In a democratic country, persuading public is a key factor to get votes, attain power and remain in power. Political leaders attain their goal by applying rhetoric in their speeches.

Rhetoric has a long history stemming from the Greeks and Romans. Greek philosopher Aristotle (384-322 B.C.) has described rhetoric as the art of discovering the means of persuasion available for any subject. This discovery requires scientific investigation. For Aristotle, most of the work for persuasion is not in making a speech to a judge or an audience; instead most of the work of rhetoric is thinking in mind the best argument one could possibly come up with that would persuade the audience or judge. Aristotle has demonstrated two ways of persuasion and named it 'Rhetorical Proofs'. Aristotle's Rhetorical Proofs are the means of persuasion; it can be Inartistic or Artistic. Inartistic Proofs are external proofs like testimonies, statistics, witnesses and documents which are not in control of the speaker. On the other hand, Artistic Proofs are internal proofs that the speaker creates in his speech. Artistic proofs are of three types, namely Logos, Pathos and Ethos. Logos are the logical arguments produced in speech to persuade audience or judge. Pathos persuading public by arousing emotions and beliefs in audience through speech. Ethos is the way of persuasion in which character, credibility or trust of the speaker persuades audience about the point being made in speech. It is up to the speaker to use any one, two or all the three Artistic Proofs in speech to make his claim stronger.

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Cicero (106-43B.C.), one of the greatest Roman orators, has described rhetoric as speech designed to persuade. According to Cicero, "Rhetoric is one great art comprised of five lesser arts: inventio, dispositio, elocutio, memoria and pronounciatio." In his book 'De inventione', Cicero presented a series or stages for preparing and presenting speeches which are called 'Canons of Rhetoric'. The five canons of rhetoric for a speech to be effective are:

- (i) **Invention:** Invention is the generation of ideas for use in a speech (Fraleigh and Tuman, 2014). While discovering the ideas to address in his speech, the speaker might come up with many ideas but selects the most useful ideas to include in his speech. While selecting the ideas, the speaker must bear in mind the purpose of speech, audience profile and their expectations.
- (ii) **Arrangement:** Arrangement refers to the structuring ideas to convey them effectively to an audience, often referred to today as organization (Fraleigh and Tuman, 2014). Speaker should order main points of the speech to make it memorable and clear to audience.
- (iii) **Style:** Style refers to the choice of language that will best express a speaker's ideas to the audience (Fraleigh and Tuman, 2014). Speaker can use figurative language for creating impact.
- (iv) **Memory:** Memory refers to the work that speakers do to remain in command of their material when they present a speech (Fraleigh and Tuman, 2014). Speakers should memorize key points, make short notes and practice or rehearse before delivering speech.
- (v) **Delivery:** Delivery refers to the speaker's use of his or her voice and body [and other elements] during the actual presentation of a speech (Fraleigh and Tuman, 2014). Delivery talks about the nonverbal part of the communication which includes facial expressions, voice tone, gesture, posture and eye-contact made by the speaker.

1.1 Major Rhetorical Devices

A rhetorical device is use of language to persuade and have an effect on audience. It is particular type of sentence structure, sound or pattern to evoke emotions and reactions from audience. Some major rhetorical devices are Accumulation, Alliteration, Allusion, Amplification, Analogy, Anaphora, Antithesis, Assonance, Chiasmus, Concession, Consonance, Epistrophe, Epizeuxis, Hypophora, Imagery, Juxtaposition, Metaphor, Parallel Structure, Parallelism, Personification, Procatlepsis, Rhetorical Question, Satire, Simile, Tricolon and Understatement. Definitions and examples of these rhetorical devices are available at <https://literarydevices.net/> website.

Aim: This research paper aims to find the Rhetorical devices and Non-verbal cues used in Indian political oratory in 21st century.

Objectives: Objectives of this research paper is to

- Identify the rhetorical devices used in speeches delivered by Indian political leaders;
- Describe the non-verbal cues surfaced during speech delivery by Indian political leaders.

2. Methodology

This paper deals with two out of five canons of rhetoric i.e. 'Style' and 'Delivery' in Indian context. In order to fulfill given objectives, Neo-rhetorical criticism of videos of recorded speeches has been carried out.

Each and every sentence spoken by Indian political leaders has been analyzed to find out all the rhetorical devices distributed in their speeches; but chosen only those sentences which applied rhetorical devices. The sentence or a set of sentences considered as a single unit for scrutiny has been termed as 'Speech Unit'.

Sample: Since the paper is about political oratory in Indian context; so purposive sampling has been used to determine the sample. The sample constitutes speeches delivered by Indian Prime Ministers when addressing the nation for the first time on Independence Day. 21st century has seen the rise of two Prime Ministers by now. Dr. Manmohan Singh and Narendra Modi have addressed the nation for the first time in 2004 and 2014 respectively. Video recordings of these speeches of Dr. Manmohan Singh and Narendra Modi have been downloaded from Youtube channel of Prasar Bharti Archives & Doordarshan National respectively. Thus two speeches delivered by Prime Ministers of India have been analyzed for this study.

3. Findings

The study revealed different rhetorical devices used by Indian political leaders and their non-verbal cues i.e. facial expressions, intonation, eye-contact, gesture, posture surfaced during speech. Findings from the study has been presented into two parts,

- In the first part, analysis of speech delivered by Dr. Manmohan Singh on 58th Independence Day has been presented;
- Second part presents the analysis of speech delivered by Mr. Narendra Modi on 68th Independence Day.

3.1 Analysis of speech delivered by Dr. Manmohan Singh on 58th Independence Day

Table 1.1: Frequency of Rhetorical devices used in Dr. Manmohan Singh's first address to the nation as Prime Minister on 58th Independence Day

Serial no.	Rhetorical Device	Frequency
1	Accumulation	6
2	Alliteration	1
3	Allusion	8
4	Analogy	2
5	Anaphora	1
6	Antithesis	1
7	Chiasmus	1
8	Consonance	2
9	Hypophora	2
10	Juxtaposition	2
11	Metaphor	4
12	Parallel Structure	1
13	Parallelism	3
14	Personification	1
15	Simile	3
16	Tricolon	1
17	Understatement	1
	Total	40

Non-verbal cues surfaced during Dr. Manmohan Singh's first address to the nation as Prime Minister on 58th Independence Day

Facial Expression: When talking about pride on country or soldiers, facial expression of Dr. Manmohan Singh did not support what he said. The same is true for any other emotion he expressed verbally.

Voice: Dr. Manmohan Singh delivers his whole speech at consistent pace and volume. He uttered every word clearly and took pauses multiple times within a sentence. While asking

questions to audience, instead of taking pause in order to make them think, he provided answers quickly. Though he put emphasis on words, his speech delivery was without intonation.

Eyes: In order to read speech from the paper, Dr. Manmohan Singh had to look down every now and then. Thus he was not able to maintain eye-contact with audience.

Gesture: Dr. Manmohan Singh kept his hand low. His hands were visible only at the end of speech when he asked children to acclaim 'Jai Hind'. Besides this, slight head movements have been made by him during speech.

Posture: Upper body of Dr. Manmohan Singh was leaning forward while delivering speech.

3.2 Analysis of speech delivered by Mr. Narendra Modi on 68th Independence Day

Table 1.2: Frequency of Rhetorical devices used in Mr. Narendra Modi's first address to the nation as Prime Minister on 68th Independence Day

Serial no.	Rhetorical Device	Frequency
1	Accumulation	1
2	Alliteration	4
3	Allusion	4
4	Amplification	3
5	Analogy	7
6	Anaphora	1
7	Antithesis	3
8	Concession	1
9	Consonance	9
10	Epistrophe	20
11	Epizeuxis	5
12	Hypophora	8
13	Imagery	2
14	Juxtaposition	10
15	Metaphor	4
16	Parallel Structure	16
17	Parallelism	3
18	Personification	1
19	Procatlepsis	2
20	Rhetorical Question	11
21	Satire	2
22	Tricolon	13
	Total	130

Non-verbal cues surfaced during Mr. Narendra Modi's first address to the nation as Prime Minister on 68th Independence Day

Facial Expression: Many emotions are visible on Narendra Modi's face. His facial expressions support the emotions expressed through his words. He also gave a friendly smile to audience a few times during speech.

Voice: Narendra Modi produced variation in volume and pace during his speech. He started speech with low pace and gradually increased it. He put emphasis on certain words to grab audience's attention toward that idea. On the other side, his volume of voice is so low at few places that his last words or sentences are not clear. He also left some sentences incomplete. He delivered his whole speech in rising intonation. With the help of intonation he was able to

utter some simple sentences as questions. After asking questions he took pause every time so that the audience could think of its answer.

Eyes: While delivering speech Narendra Modi continuously moved his whole body from one side to another. Sometimes he looked down to the notes prepared for speech but he did not read whole speech from the script. These factors helped him maintaining eye-contact with audience.

Gesture: Hands of Narendra Modi created vivid pictures of what he said. He used wide variety of gestures to express his words. Some common gestures surfaced during his speech are Clenched Fist, Pointing with Index Finger, Okay Sign, Hand Plateau, Open Palm and wave. He created gestures with his hands above the shoulders, in front of shoulders and side of shoulders. When refuting an idea, he nodded his head horizontally. His words are synchronized with gestures.

Posture: Narendra Modi stand straight while delivering speech. On few occasions he put his hands on podium.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

Dr. Manmohan Singh and Narendra Modi are the only Indian Prime Ministers who addressed the Nation for the first time on Independence Day in 21st century. Dr. Manmohan Singh was an academician and adorned many high ranking posts in various government offices. In his early career, he has been an official person; thus less experienced in delivering speeches. He speaks less and has soft voice. He was never a member of Loksabha. Narendra Modi has always entered government by winning elections. His keen interest in debates and theatre reflects in his political speeches. Although some political analystcriticizes him on the ground of authenticity of the information produced by him, he is undoubtedly a good orator.

Dr. Manmohan Singh (2004) and Narendra Modi (2014) addressed the nation on Independence Day for approximately 43 minutes and 65 minutes respectively. In his speech, Dr. Manmohan Singh used 17 types of rhetorical device 40 times whereas Narendra Modi applied the rhetorical device technique 130 times which are of 22 types.

While delivering speech, facial expressions of Dr. Manmohan Singh did not match with his words while Narendra Modi's did. Narendra Modi maintained eye-contact with

audience but Dr. Manmohan Singh was not able to do so as he was reading from paper. Voice of Dr. Manmohan Singh was monotonous while Narendra Modi switched his tone accordingly. Hands of Dr. Manmohan Singh was all time down during speech but Narendra Modi communicates with his hand by making different gestures. Narendra Modi stood straight on podium whereas Dr. Manmohan Singh was leaning forward. Maintaining eye-contact, voice modulation, use of wide variety of gestures, appropriate posture and synchronized facial expressions are the key aspects of speech delivery and speech of Narendra Modi contains all of it.

In the age of internet, social media and TV news channels; importance of speech making is highly increased because it can be broadcasted LIVE to all over the world. So, each and every aspect of speech making should be handled with great care in order to generate desired response from public. On the grounds of speech 'Style' and 'Delivery', speech delivered by Narendra Modi is successful. He has applied rhetorical device 130 times in his 65 minute speech with appropriate nonverbal cues. On contrary, Dr. Manmohan Singh applied rhetorical devices 40 times in his 43 minutes speech with limited nonverbal cues. He speaks less whereas Narendra Modi has an image of world class orator. Thus it is evident that use of rhetorical devices and appropriate nonverbal cues in speeches has profound effect over Indian public. According to political analyst Pushpesh Pant, "A good political speech should have an emotional charge; it should have credibility and a subtle sense of humor woven into it. Modi's speech managed all three." Rhetorical devices and nonverbal cues in political speeches generate emotional response from public. Speech delivered by Narendra Modi is full of Rhetorical Devices and Non-verbal cues which evokes emotions of public.

Rakesh Batabyal has advocated the need of research on Narendra Modi's speeches in an article as "His speeches need to be analyzed at greater length because of their influence and sheer volume of words that he has spoken."¹ Further, he proposes "It is up to the media, public intellectuals and political parties to question & analyze public speeches and expose if necessary, the fallacies and the false propaganda, if any."² Undoubtedly, oratory skills are a must for Indian political leaders to be successful in present era. Politicians should put an effort to learn do's and don'ts of oratory. Institutes should be open up to train future leaders in public speaking. Besides, speeches should be designed to be TV events so that it could produce desired effect over maximum people.

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